

Comparative analysis of k - ω SST model and porous approach for HTGR core section calculation*

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Abstract

This study presents a comparative analysis of two geometric representations of the flow domain for RANS simulations of a high-temperature gas-cooled reactor (HTGR) core segment: a realistic model with explicitly resolved fuel pebbles and a porous-medium representation based on volume-averaged properties. The computations were performed with the LOGOS software package using the k - ω SST turbulence model. The realistic model reproduces local flow and heat-transfer features of helium, including recirculation, local acceleration in interstitial gaps, and temperature hot spots, with peak values of 2.69 m/s and 1310 K. In contrast, the porous-medium approach yields a spatially smoothed solution with markedly lower extrema: the maximum velocity does not exceed 0.5 m/s and the maximum temperature is 727 K. Using precomputed resistance coefficients, the porous model predicts an average helium velocity in the pebble bed that is 76.4% lower, while the mean temperature and pressure drop differ by about 9%. The realistic representation is preferable when local thermal-hydraulic quantities are required, e.g., for transient and accident analyses. The porous-medium approximation, owing to its computational efficiency, is well suited for preliminary calculations and integral assessments in large computational domains, provided that the model is properly parameterized.

Keywords

CFD, HTGR, LOGOS, VHTR, porosity, TRISO

Introduction

High-temperature gas-cooled reactors (HTGRs) are among the most promising Generation IV systems, combining high operational reliability, inherent safety features, and high thermal efficiency. The helium outlet temperature from the core can reach 950 °C, which makes HTGRs attractive for industrial applications ranging from cogeneration and hydrogen production to process heat supply for metallurgy and the chemical industry (Fütterer et al. 2014; Sato et al. 2015). A prominent HTGR concept is the pebble-bed HTGR (PB-HTGR), in which the fuel

is encapsulated in spherical graphite pebbles containing TRISO particles. This architecture enables high core temperatures, modularity, and continuous online fuel loading and unloading.

The HTR-10 reactor developed at Tsinghua University (China) serves as an international reference for the verification and validation of numerical models, including within IAEA benchmark activities. It has a thermal power of 10 MW, a core with a diameter of 180 cm and a height of 197 cm, and a helium outlet temperature of up to 1000 K (Ahmed et al. 2021). Thermal-hydraulic analysis of a PB-HTGR core is challenging due to complex

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flow patterns in an anisotropic medium, including local heterogeneities, recirculation regions, and non-uniform heat transfer (Almusafir et al. 2023). In CFD, two geometric representations are commonly adopted to describe these processes: a realistic approach with explicitly resolved fuel pebbles and a porous-medium approach, where the medium properties are volume-averaged and the flow resistance is introduced via additional momentum-source terms.

Both approaches are frequently implemented within a RANS framework for turbulent flows using the k- ω SST turbulence model. The porous-medium representation substantially reduces computational cost and can provide acceptable accuracy for integral quantities such as the pressure gradient (pressure drop) and the temperature field (Avramenko et al. 2021; Wu et al. 2010). However, it cannot reproduce key local phenomena, including vortex formation, flow separation, and directional heat-transfer effects (Huning et al. 2021). The porous approximation has been employed, for example, in simulations of the SANA experiments (Becker and Laurien 2003) and in studies of tritium permeation from the breeding zone into the coolant region (Guo et al. 2006). In practice, the choice of method depends on the modeling objectives and the required level of spatial detail.

With increasing requirements for safety substantiation and efficiency assessment of next-generation nuclear systems, as well as the growing role of CFD in the design and modernization of nuclear power facilities (Bolshov et al. 2020; Orlov and Gabaraev 2023), there is a clear need for a quantitative evaluation of the applicability of each approach to the thermal-hydraulic analysis of HTGR-type reactors. This is particularly important for transient and accident scenarios (e.g., LOCA), where accurate

prediction of local temperatures and velocities may be critical (Berens et al. 2025; Guo et al. 2021).

In the present study, the HTR-10 reactor is considered as a benchmark object for a comparative assessment of realistic and porous-medium approaches within RANS simulations of steady-state helium flow using k- ω SST turbulence model in the LOGOS software package. The work aims to examine how the choice of approach affects flow features, temperature and pressure distributions, and to formulate practical recommendations for engineering CFD applications to HTGRs.

Materials and methods

As a rule, the explicit motion of pebble fuel elements is not modeled. Instead, a separate pre-processing step is performed to generate a packed-bed configuration and determine the pebble locations; these positions are then fixed for subsequent thermal-hydraulic or neutronic simulations (Blandford et al. 2020).

Mathematical model

The LOGOS software suite provides several turbulence-modeling levels, including RANS, LES, DES, and DNS. In the present work, both the realistic and porous-medium approaches are based on the RANS formulation with the k- ω SST turbulence model proposed by Menter (Menter et al. 2003). RANS models have proven to be a computationally efficient tool for preliminary coolant-flow analysis.

When the Menter turbulence model is written in terms of the turbulent kinetic energy and the specific dissipation rate, it can be expressed as:

$$\begin{cases} \frac{D(\rho k)}{Dt} = \nabla [(\mu + \sigma_k \mu_T) \nabla k] + P_k - \beta^* \rho \omega k \\ \frac{D(\rho \omega)}{Dt} = \nabla [(\mu + \sigma_\omega \mu_T) \nabla \omega] + \gamma \frac{\rho}{\mu_T} P_k - \beta^* \rho \omega^2 + (1 - F_1) D_{k\omega} \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

Where k is the turbulent kinetic energy (m^2/s^2); ω is the specific dissipation rate (s^{-1}); ρ is the density (kg/m^3); P_k is the production term; μ is the dynamic viscosity ($Pa \cdot s$); μ_T is the turbulent viscosity ($Pa \cdot s$); F_1 is a blending function; $D_{k\omega}$ is the dissipation term (W/m^3); and σ_k , σ_ω , β^* , γ are empirical model constants.

A porous body resists the flow due to viscous (dissipative) and inertial effects, which are volume-averaged. Mathematically, fluid motion in a porous medium is described by the Brinkman-Forchheimer equations, which can be viewed as the Navier-Stokes equations augmented with resistance terms (Kozelkov et al. 2018):

$$\begin{cases} \nabla \cdot (\varphi \rho \mathbf{u}) = 0 \\ \nabla \cdot (\varphi \rho \mathbf{u} \otimes \mathbf{u}) = -\varphi \nabla(p \mathbf{I}) + \nabla \cdot (\varphi \boldsymbol{\tau}) - \left(\frac{\varphi^2 \mu}{\mathbf{K}} + \varphi^3 F \mathbf{C} |\mathbf{u}| \right) \cdot \mathbf{u} \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

where $\varphi = V_{\text{por}} / V_{\text{tot}}$ is the porosity; V_{por} is the pore volume (m^3); V_{tot} is the total volume of the computational domain (m^3); \mathbf{u} is the velocity vector; p is the static pressure (Pa); \mathbf{I} is the second-order identity tensor; $\boldsymbol{\tau}$ is the viscous stress tensor for an incompressible

fluid; \mathbf{K} is the permeability tensor; F is the empirical Forchheimer coefficient; and \mathbf{C} is the inertial-resistance tensor.

With Eq. (2) taken into account, the system in Eq. (1) can be rewritten as:

$$\begin{cases} \frac{\partial(\varphi \rho k)}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot (\varphi \rho \mathbf{u} k) = \nabla [(\mu + \sigma_k \mu_T) \nabla k] + \varphi P_k - \varphi \beta^* \rho \omega k, \\ \frac{\partial(\varphi \rho \omega)}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot (\varphi \rho \mathbf{u} \omega) = \nabla [(\mu + \sigma_\omega \mu_T) \nabla \omega] + \varphi \gamma \frac{\rho}{\mu_T} P_k - \varphi \beta^* \rho \omega^2 + (1 - F_1) D_{k\omega} \end{cases} \quad (3)$$

The porous-medium resistance term in Eq. (2) may be represented as:

$$\left(\frac{\phi^2 \mu}{\mathbf{K}} + \phi^3 F C |\mathbf{u}| \right) \cdot \mathbf{u} = (\beta + \alpha |\mathbf{u}|) \cdot \mathbf{u} \quad (4)$$

where $\beta \cdot \mathbf{u}$ is the Darcy (linear viscous) term proportional to the velocity vector, accounting for the flow resistance caused by viscous interaction of the fluid with the solid matrix (an analogue of Darcy's law); and $\alpha |\mathbf{u}| \cdot \mathbf{u}$ is the Forchheimer (nonlinear inertial) term accounting for additional losses associated with inertial effects at higher flow velocities, driven by local accelerations and recirculation.

For an isotropic porous medium, the linear resistance coefficient can be obtained from Darcy's law as:

$$\beta = \frac{\mu}{\mathbf{K}} = \frac{\Delta p}{u h} \quad (5)$$

where Δp is the pressure drop across the porous section (Pa), and h is the height of the porous section (m).

Geometrical model

This study considers the central region of the HTR-10 reactor core. The computational domain has a height of 820 mm and a square cross-section of 87×87 mm. The 60 mm diameter fuel pebbles are arranged in a face-centered cubic (FCC) lattice. The porosity of the pebble-filled region in the computational model is 0.336. Fig. 1 shows the geometrical models employed for simulations using the realistic and porous-medium approaches. Owing to the internal symmetry of the considered segment, the porous medium is assumed to be isotropic.

Boundary conditions and material properties

The boundary-condition parameters were specified based on the data reported in Ahmed et al. (2021). In both computational domains, the inlet mass flow rate was set to 0.01176 kg/s and the helium inlet temperature to 523 K. At the outlet, the helium pressure was prescribed as 7 MPa. Symmetry boundary conditions were applied on the lateral surfaces. For the realistic geometry, the heat flux was imposed on the surface of each pebble belonging to the corresponding axial zone (Fig. 1), whereas in the porous-medium approximation the volumetric heat generation rate was prescribed in each zone according to Table 1. In addition, the porous model requires the linear resistance coefficient β . Since no experimental pressure-drop data were available, β was evaluated from the pressure drops

Figure 1. Geometrical models for the realistic (left) and porous-medium (right) approaches.

obtained in the simulations with the realistic geometry using Eq. (5) for each zone of the computational domain.

The thermophysical properties of helium were defined using the temperature-dependent correlations given in Ahmed et al. (2021). For the evaluation of similarity numbers and pressure drops in Section 3.4, the properties were taken as averaged values at 7 MPa and 650 K: density $\rho = 4.33$ kg/m³; dynamic viscosity $\mu = 3.85 \cdot 10^{-5}$ Pa·s; thermal conductivity $\lambda = 0.31$ W/(m·K); and specific heat capacity $C_p = 5195$ J/(kg·K).

For a characteristic inlet velocity in the considered porous section of $u = 0.358$ m/s and a pebble diameter of $d_p = 0.06$ m, the Reynolds number is $Re = 2440$. To account for the effect of porosity, modified Reynolds numbers were also calculated: $Re_m = 3789$ for the section with $\phi = 0.361$ and $Re_m = 3524$ for the section with $\phi = 0.313$. The Prandtl number is $Pr = 0.645$.

Mesh-convergence assessment

The results obtained with RANS approaches are sensitive to mesh resolution and near-wall treatment. To ensure that the present simulations are effectively independent of the cell size, a mesh-convergence assessment was performed for both the realistic and porous-medium representations using the pressure drop and the maximum helium velocity as key metrics. Because meshing and resolving the near-contact regions between adjacent pebbles is challenging, a near-touching approximation was adopted, in which a small clearance is introduced between

Table 1. Simulation parameters

Computational-domain zone	Zone length, m	Volumetric heat generation, MW/m ³	Heat flux at pebble surface, kW/m ²	β , kg/(m ³ ·s)	ϕ
Zone 1	0.1170	4.45	69.7	404	0.361
Zone 2	0.1305	5.08	73.9	362	0.313
Zone 3	0.1305	5.41	78.8	362	0.313
Zone 4	0.1170	5.14	80.5	214	0.361

the spheres. In the present work, this gap is 1.52 mm. This approach is widely used in CFD studies of HTGR-type pebble-bed cores (Ahmed et al. 2021; Ferng and Lin 2014; Li et al. 2012).

Mesh convergence for the realistic approach

Because the pressure drop and the maximum velocity obtained on the 6.91 million and 9.47 million-cell meshes differ by less than 0.5%, the 6.91 million-cell mesh was selected to achieve an acceptable computational cost (Fig. 2). The near-wall resolution is characterized by $y^+ = 1.08$. The adopted mesh is shown in Fig. 3 (left).

Mesh convergence for the porous-medium approach

For the porous-medium approximation, the pressure drop and the maximum helium velocity in the considered section were essentially invariant with respect to mesh refinement. To obtain a smoother interpolation of the axial temperature distribution, a mesh with 25,000 cells was used. The mesh is shown in Fig. 3 (right).

Since no experimental data are available for HTR-10, the credibility of the numerical results was assessed at the verification stage by analyzing mesh convergence and discretization uncertainty in accordance with the recommendations of Lu et al. (2025). For two overlapping mesh triplets, Nos. 4-5-6 and 5-6-7 (Fig. 2), the Grid Convergence Index (GCI) values (Table 2) were calculated for the pressure drop and the maximum helium velocity;

Table 2. GCI values for two mesh triplets

Parameter	GCI (%)	
	Mesh triplet 4-5-6	Mesh triplet 5-6-7
Δp , Pa	0	0,5
u_{max} , m/s	5,7	1,9

the detailed evaluation procedure is given in Hassan et al. (2022). The resulting GCI values for the finest triplet do not exceed 5%, which is consistent with the asymptotic grid-independence criterion and indicates a low level of discretization uncertainty when the equation residuals are reduced below 10^{-6} . Model-form and parametric uncertainties (e.g., sensitivity to the turbulent Prandtl number) were not assessed and may be addressed in future work.

Results and discussion

Overall simulation results

For the realistic geometry (6.97 million cells), the computations were performed on 14 CPU threads (AMD Ryzen 7 5800H) and required approximately 20,000 s (5.5 h) to reach the prescribed residual convergence criterion of 10^{-6} . In contrast, the porous-medium approximation (25,000 cells) was completed in 4 s, demonstrating the key advantage of this approach in terms of computational efficiency.

Figure 2. Mesh convergence for the realistic approach.

Figure 3. Computational meshes for the realistic-geometry approach (left, 6.91 million cells) and the porous-medium approach (right).

An analysis of the velocity, temperature, and pressure fields revealed pronounced qualitative differences between the two approaches (Figs 4–8).

Comparison of velocity fields

In the realistic approach, the axial helium velocity was evaluated in two ways:

- Peak velocities were obtained from vertical sections of the modeled segment by extracting the maximum values between successive pebble layers (Fig. 6).
- Section-averaged velocities were calculated over horizontal planes passing through the centers of the pebbles in each layer (Fig. 7).

For the porous-medium approximation, the axial-velocity distribution was evaluated in the mid-plane of the symmetric geometry. The results show a substantial discrepancy between the approaches. The maximum (peak) helium velocities predicted by the realistic model range from 2.54 to 2.69 m/s and occur in narrow inter-pebble gaps, where the flow accelerates due to local contraction of the available flow area. Such effects cannot be captured by the porous-medium model, in which the maximum velocity reaches only 0.5 m/s (Fig. 6).

At the outlet of the computational section, the mean axial helium velocity predicted by the porous-medium

Figure 4. Helium velocity, temperature, and pressure fields in the realistic geometry.

approach is underestimated by 43.6% relative to the realistic model. Within the pebble-bed region, the section-averaged helium velocity is 1.82 m/s for the realistic approach and 0.43 m/s for the porous-medium approach, corresponding to a deviation of 76.4%. This discrepancy arises because the porous model does not resolve local accelerations and flow-area constrictions, which play a key role in shaping the flow structure in a densely packed bed (Fig. 7).

Overall, the realistic approach provides a more detailed representation of the flow, including recirculation and shear regions, whereas the porous-medium approximation yields a spatially smoothed, volume-averaged picture and systematically underpredicts key hydrodynamic parameters.

Figure 5. Helium velocity, temperature, and pressure fields in the realistic geometry for different sections.

Figure 6. Helium velocity for the realistic approach (vertical plane through the peak-velocity region) and the porous-medium approach.

Figure 7. Section-averaged helium velocities in horizontal planes for the realistic approach.

Temperature comparison

The axial profile of the section-averaged helium temperature (Fig. 8) shows that the realistic approach reproduces the temperature gradients and local maxima more accurately. The peak temperature differs by 44.6% between the approaches (1310 K versus 730 K). The outlet-averaged temperature is 800 K in the realistic case and 727 K in the porous-medium case, corresponding to a 9% discrepancy.

The lower temperatures predicted by the porous-medium model are attributed to an underestimation of local velocities and, consequently, of the convective heat-transfer contribution. This may be particularly important for safety-related analyses, where limiting heat loads and fuel-temperature margins are evaluated.

Figure 8. Axial distribution of the mean helium temperature in the modeled section.

Pressure-drop comparison

A comparison of the pressure drop predicted by the two approaches is provided in Table 3. Despite the simplified geometry, the porous-medium approach reproduces the pressure drop within 9% of the realistic simulation (Table 3). This agreement is primarily due to the use of the linear resistance coefficient β , which was derived from the pressure drops obtained in the realistic-geometry simulations (Table 1). The accuracy of the porous-medium approximation

Table 3. Pressure drop for the realistic and porous-medium approaches and empirical correlations

Approach / correlation	Δp , Pa	Deviation, % (realistic / porous)
Realistic	67	+9.0
Porous-medium	73	
Ergun equation	150	-55.3 / -51.3
Leva correlation	53	+26.4 / +37.7
Handley and Heggs correlation	79	-15.2 / -7.6
Tallmadge correlation	74	-9.5 / -1.4

therefore strongly depends on model parameterization: applying the derived coefficients outside the context of the original geometry, or under different flow and heat-transfer conditions, requires additional validation, which limits the predictive reliability of the approach.

To assess the physical consistency of the results, the CFD-predicted pressure drops were compared with values obtained from several empirical correlations for pebble beds. In addition to the classical Ergun equation (6) (Akgiray and Saatçı 2001), the correlations of Leva (7), Handley and Heggs (8), and Tallmadge (9) reported in Hassan and Kang (2012). Table 3 summarizes the relative deviations of the CFD pressure drops: 67 Pa for the realistic approach and 73 Pa for the porous-medium approach from the values predicted by these correlations.

The Ergun equation yields a pressure drop of approximately 150 Pa, whereas the CFD simulations give 67 Pa (realistic) and 73 Pa (porous-medium). Closer values (53–79 Pa) are obtained using the Leva, Handley-Heggs, and Tallmadge correlations, which were developed for a broad range of porosities and flow regimes. According to Hassan et al. (2022), their applicability generally covers $Re < 20000$, pebble diameters from 31.7 mm to 95.2 mm, and porosities in the range 0.30–0.42, with a typical correlation uncertainty of 10–15%. As noted in Li and Ji (2015), the classical Ergun equation tends to over-predict pressure losses at $Re > 1000$, because the coefficients in its empirical terms depend on the bed structure and are not universal for regular packings such as FCC.

Hence, discrepancies among the correlations and between the correlations and CFD results can be attributed to both the structural characteristics of the pebble arrangement and differences in porosity. In the present work, the Tallmadge correlation shows the best agreement with the CFD results (Table 3), with deviations of 9.5% for the realistic approach and 1.4% for the porous-medium approach, which is within its stated uncertainty of 10%.

$$\frac{\Delta p}{L} = \frac{150 \cdot \mu}{\rho g} \frac{(1 - \phi)^2}{\phi^3} \frac{\mu \cdot u}{d_p^2} + 1,75 \frac{(1 - \phi)}{\phi^3} \frac{\rho u^2}{d_p} \quad (6)$$

$$\frac{\Delta p}{L} = 200 \left(\frac{\mu u}{d_p^2} \right) \frac{(1 - \phi)^2}{\phi^3} + 1,75 \frac{(1 - \phi)}{\phi^3} \frac{\rho u^2}{d_p} \quad (7)$$

$$\frac{\Delta p}{L} = 368 \left(\frac{\mu u}{d_p^2} \right) \frac{(1 - \phi)^2}{\phi^3} + 1,24 \frac{(1 - \phi)}{\phi^3} \frac{\rho u^2}{d_p} \quad (8)$$

$$\frac{\Delta p}{L} = \left(\frac{\mu u}{d_p^2} \right) \frac{(1 - \phi)^2}{\phi^3} (150 + 4,2 \text{Re}_m^{0,833}) \quad (9)$$

where L is the length of the porous section (m; Table 1); d_p is the pebble diameter (m); u is the inlet velocity into the porous section (m/s); and Re_m is the modified Reynolds number.

Conclusion

This work compared two CFD approaches for predicting the thermal-hydraulic characteristics of a core segment of the HTR-10 reactor: a realistic geometry-resolved approach and a porous-medium approach. The simulations

were performed with the Russian CFD software package LOGOS using the $k-\omega$ SST turbulence model.

The results show that the realistic approach can reproduce the key features of helium flow in the inter-pebble region, including local jetting/acceleration, recirculation zones, and a non-uniform temperature field. The peak velocity and temperature obtained in the realistic simulation (2.69 m/s and 1310 K, respectively) are substantially higher than those predicted by the porous-medium approximation (0.5 m/s and 730 K). In addition, the mean helium velocity in the pebble bed predicted by the realistic approach exceeds the porous-medium result by 76.4%, while the outlet-averaged helium temperature differs by 9%. The predicted pressure drops are comparable for the two approaches, with a deviation of about 9%. However, this agreement was achieved by calibrating the porous-medium resistance coefficients against the realistic-geometry simulations, which limits the applicability of the porous model to other configurations.

Overall, the realistic approach provides higher physical fidelity and is recommended for problems where accurate prediction of local thermal-hydraulic parameters is essential, in particular for transient and accident analyses. On the other hand, the porous-medium approximation is approximately 5000 times more computationally efficient. Therefore, it can be effectively used at early design stages, in parametric studies, and especially for assessing integral characteristics in large computational domains. Nevertheless, the porous-medium approach requires mandatory validation and tuning of model coefficients for the specific geometry and flow conditions. For full-core simulations, potential anisotropy of the pebble-bed packing should also be taken into account.

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